

To Study the Water Availability and Requirement of Solapur District from A Geographical Perspective

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Introduction:

Water is essential for all forms of life and is, therefore, invaluable. Although, a renewable natural resource, water is exhaustible and has multiple uses and hence, various demands. In many areas, semi-arid and hard-rock region in Solapur district. Water resources have almost been completely exhausted and now water is not easily available even for drinking purpose. An attempt has been made to study and analyse, the competing availability, and requirement in Solapur district. The demand for water for domestic, agricultural, and industrial uses in Solapur significantly exceeds the quantity of water available. This has led to conflicts among various uses as well as users of water.

Water scarcity is among the main problems to be faced by society, in 21st century. Water scarcity is commonly defined as a situation where water availability in a region is below 1000³ per person per year. However, many areas are in Solapur district, which experience much more severe scarcity, living with less than 500 m³ per person per year, which could be considered as severe water scarcity. The threshold of 2000 m³ per person per year is conserved to indicate that a region is water stressed since under these conditions populations face also problems, but whenever, a drought occurs or when man made shortage are being created. However, the concept

of water availability based on indicators driven from the renewable water resources divided by the total population should be taken with great care. This simple indicator may not be very meaningful in situation where district make high use of desalination, of non-renewable groundwater resources and waste water reuse to compensate for their scarcity of renewable water. This may also be true for Solapur district, where irrigation water requirement are not large. Water scarcity causes enormous problems for the population and societies. The available water is not sufficient for the production of food and for alleviating hunger and poverty in the Solapur district, where quite often the population growth is larger than the capability for sustainable use of the natural resources. The lack of water does not allow industrial, urban and tourism development to proceed without restrictions on water uses and allocation policies for other user sector, particularly agriculture. Mankind, most serious challenge in the 21st Century might not be war or hunger or disease or even the collapse of civic order, it may be the lack of fresh water.

Keywords: Availability Water, Requirement Water, Scarcity, Domestic, Industrial, Livestock, Irrigation.

Objectives:

1. To study the availability and requirements of water in Solapur District.
2. Planning water according to water requirements.

Study Area:

The Solapur district is lies in the Bhima-Sina-Man basins, just before the Bhima river leaves Maharashtra state to enter in Karnataka state. It is located in between 17°10' North to 18°32' North latitudes and 74°42' East to 76°15' East longitudes. The district is fairly well defined to its west as well as east by the inward-looking scraps of Mahadeo hills range and the osmanabad plateau. The adjoining districts are Sangali to its southwest, Satara to its west, Pune to northwest, Ahmadnagar to its north, Beed & Osmanabad to its east and the Bijapur district of Karnataka state to its south. The district is divided into eleven tahsils to its administrative purpose, which constitute 1150 villages and 13 urban areas. These tahsils are Karmala, Madha, Barshi, North Solapur, Solapur South, Mohol, Pandharpur, Malshiras, Sangola, Mangalwedha, Akkalkot. The total population of district was 43,15,527 persons in which male & female were 22,33,778 and 20,81,749 respectively according to 2011 censusStudy Area

The regions under studies constitute about 4.88 present area and about 4.51 present population of Maharashtra state. It ranks fourth in terms of area and seventh in term of population among the district of Maharashtra. The district occupies the total geographical area of 14,889 square 65ilometer and holds fourth ranks in Maharashtra state

Methodology:

The basic unit of investigation will be district as well as the talukas .The collected data is processed and edited the various cartographic

and quantitative as well as statistical method would be used analysis of different aspect of proposal study. The collected data have been processed and presented thought the tables and maps. Solapur district has been considered as an aerial unit

Table 1: Yearly Estimated Water Requirement for Different Uses in Solapur District.

(Million cubic meter/yearly)

District	Domestic Use	Livestock	Industrial Use	Irrigation	Total
Solapur	210	130	260	1268	1868

Fig. 1

Water supply and sanitation are important basic needs for the improvement of the quality of life and enhancement of productive efficiency of the people. In urban and rural areas, water is tapped for domestic and industrial uses from rivers, streams, wells and lakes. Almost 80 percent of the water is supplied for domestic use, comes out as wastewater. In most of the cases wastewater is let out untreated and it either sinks into the ground as a potential pollutant of ground water or is discharged in to the natural drainage system casusing pollution in downstream areas in Solapur district about 78 percent of the urban population has access to safe drinking water and about 38 percent of the urban population has access to sanitation services. Water requirement

for various sector is given table 5.9. This indicates that demand for drinking water is increasing, since the population in urban areas is rapidly increasing

Yearly Estimated Water Requirement for Different Uses in Solapur District:

Yearly estimated water requirement for different uses in Solapur district is illustrated in table 5.9. The total requirement of water for the district as whole is 1868 million cubic meter per year. The total requirement of the for the Solapur district is grouped in to Four major uses, which is Domestic, Livestock, Industrial, and Irrigation purposes.

The highest use of water is for irrigation purpose which is 1268 million cubic meter per year. A part from this the industrial uses of water ranks second in Solapur district, which comes to 260 million cubic meter, per year. This shows that the irrigation for the agriculture purposes is most dominant sector, for utilization of water in Solapur district, no doubt industrial sector also relatively consume sizable amount of water in Solapur district. The domestic uses of the water ranks Third in Solapur district which accounts to 210 million cubic meter per year. The livestock uses of the water is comparatively small which is 130 million cubic meter in Solapur district per year. This has been also represented by pie diagram in Fig.5.7

Table 2: Water Requirement for Different Uses in Solapur District 2013-14

(Million cubic meter /year)

S.N	Tahsil	Population	Percentage of population	Domestic Uses	Livestock	Industrial Uses	Irrigation	Total
	Use of water		100	210	130	260	1268	1868
1	Karmala	254777	6.07	3.1	5.15	2.57	0.52	11.37
2	Madha	323727	7.60	3.6	5.84	2.92	0.59	12.95
3	Barshi	372416	5.89	2.8	4.46	2.23	0.45	9.94
4	N.Solapur	1056312	24.96	11.8	19.15	9.57	1.96	42.48
5	Mohol	276656	6.56	3.1	5.00	2.51	0.51	11.12
6	Pandharpur	442173	10.46	4.9	8.00	4.00	0.82	17.72
7	Malshiras	485440	10.97	5.22	8.38	4.19	0.85	18.64
8	Sangola	323418	7.06	3.6	5.84	2.92	0.59	12.95
9	Mangalwedha	206147	4.45	2.11	3.42	1.71	0.34	7.58
10	S.Solapur	260046	5.48	2.60	4.21	2.10	0.42	9.33
11	Akkalkot	314415	7.54	3.54	5.76	2.88	0.59	12.77
	Total District	4315527	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Compiled by Researcher based on water supply report Hydrology Department of Delhi

With total population of 4.3 million as per 2011 censuses for the district as a whole, the use of water is 1868 million cubic meter per year. As stated in the present discussion that the highest amount of water is used for irrigation purpose in agricultural sector. It is also expected, that the size of population is directly related with the use of water in Solapur district. It is clearly indicated

by the different uses of water in North Solapur tahsil, the highest population of North Solapur tahsil accouts almost 25 percent population of the district, hence, the total use of water for North Solapur tahsil is 42.48 million cubic meter out of the 100 percent of the district.

Domestic Uses of Water:

The domestic use of water estimated to 210 million cubic meter per year for the entire district of Solapur. The highest domestic use of water recorded for North Solapur tahsil is owing to largest population of North Solapur tahsil on the other hand the lowest amount of domestic use of water is found for Mangalwedha tahsil, which is slightly more than two million cubic meter, as Mangalwedha has lower population in Solapur district.

The amounts of domestic use of water in order of importance have been recorded for Malshiras tahsil, Pandharpur, Sangola and Akkalkot tahsils. It is worth mentioning that remaining tahsils of the Solapur district have recorded the amount of domestic use of water between two and three million cubic meter. It may be stated briefly, that the domestic use of water is related with the size of population in each tahsil of Solapur district.

Livestock Use of Water:

For entire district of Solapur the livestock use of water is estimated 130 million cubic meter.

Among the various uses of water the livestock water is lowest which is only 130 million cubic meter. Highest amount with exception to North Solapur tahsil, the other tahsils leave behind Malshiras, Pandharpur, represent the higher use of water by livestock, while Mangalwedha, Barshi and South Solapur represent lower amount of estimated water requirement. According to size of livestock animals, the amount of water also increases in different parts of Solapur district.

Industrial Use of Water:

The industrial use of water is estimated to 260 million cubic meter for North Solapur tahsil which is one of the most industrial belt of district. Hence, the highest requirement for industrial water is for North Solapur tahsil. The industrial uses of water requirement is 9.57 million cubic meter for North Solapur tahsil. This is highest in the Solapur district. The Mangalwedha tahsil, which is most industrial backward tahsil than other tahsils in Solapur district.

Fig. 5.10

Hence, the industrial use represents only 1.7 million cubic meter. In most of the tahsils of Solapur district due to the low degree of industrialization, the amount of estimated water requirement for industrial uses is below 3.0 million cubic meter. The sizable amount of industrial use of water is also found for the Pandharpur and Malshiras tahsils. This accounts more than 4.0 million cubic meter. The degree of industrialization and concerned urbanization influences the water requirement for industrial use in different tahsils of Solapur district.

Irrigation Use of Water:

The total amount of irrigation use of water is estimated 1268 cubic million liters. Surprisingly, the highest amount of water is estimated for North Solapur tahsil. Which is 1.96 million cubic meter. It is, essential and most appropriate, at the very outset to discuss that, the existence of Solapur city in North Solapur tahsil, gets most of the vegetable fruits and milk supplied by the immediate fringe region of Solapur City. Horticulture, is practiced at vary intensive scale in the hinterland of Solapur city. The horticulture needs a quite large amount of

water for irrigation throughout the year, whereas the Rabi and Kharif crops need relatively less water for irrigation the production of Cereals need only irrigation for Rabi crops once in a year in different tahsils of Solapur district. Most of the Kharif crops depend upon the monsoon rainfall, in this way it may be concluded that North Solapur tahsil uses highest irrigation water for horticulture.

Fig. 5.11

As for as the other tahsils of Solapur district, represents less than 1.0 million cubic meter irrigation water due to Kharif monsoon predominate crops. It may be also concluded, that there is close correspondence between the irrigation uses of water and the proportions of irrigated land in Malshiras and Pandharpur tahsils which are near to 1 million cubic meter water for irrigation. Dry tahsils where the irrigation requirement of water is more also depicts values more than 0.5 for Akkalkot, Sangola, and Mohol tahsils.

Total use of Water:

The total use of water estimated at 1868 million cubic meter, for district as a whole. It is a matter of great astonishment that, the highest amount of water used by North Solapur tahsil. This is due to the existence of Solapur city; the total water is used to 42.48 million cubic meter. It is almost, more than 40 percent of the total use of water in the district. Malshirash and Pandahrpur tahsils have a sizable amount of total water use in Solapur tahsil, Sangola and Madha both represent almost 13.0 million cubic meter. Akkalkot, Mohol, Karmala represent more than 10 million cubic meter water. Total use water in the rest other tahsil of Solapur district like South Solapur, Mangalwedha and Barshi have shown less than 10 million cubic meter water . There are wide variations in the total use of water depending upon the physio-socio-economic factors.

Conclusion:

The water in relation to population the total available water in cubic meter is estimated of 176278, cubic meter this is corresponding to 458694 million liters for entire population of

Solapur distirct. There are wide variation in the availability of water in cubic meter in different tahsils of Solapur district. The highest being for Malshiras tahsil while the lowest available water is for North Solapur tahsil. There are Four criteria to understand the exact situation of water in any area. These are the availability of water demand or requirement, surpluses and deficit of water. In Indian condition the standard requirement of water per person per day is taken as 50 liters per person per day. This is the optimum level of water, per person per day for Solapur district as a whole. Only 29.11 liters per person per day water is available which is much less than the requirement of water per person per day.

The spatial pattern of available water also enormously vary from one tahsil to another. The Karmala represents the highest value of water availability which is 44 liters per person per day and it is followed by Madha tahsil which represent about 42 liter per person per day. This is because of the privilege of Ujani dam found in the vicinity of Karmala and Madha tahsil of Solapur district. It is matter of ashtonishment that the lowest value of water availability is found for the North Solapur tahsil, which is accounted 5.12 liters per person per day. This is probably due to the large population of the Solapur city which exists in North Solapur tahsil. This is concluded that as compare to the standard requirement of water per person per day of 50 liters. Almost 44 liters water per person per day is demanded by the people of North Solapur tahsil. This is the major cause to understand that the particular drinking water to the Solapur city is supplied only twice per week for a copula of hours. Now the timing of the drinking water supply is made for Wednesday and Saturday in week between 5.30 a.m. to 7.30 a.m. in Solapur city.

In 2025 it is estimated that the water potentiality will increase to 2046 million cubic meter and the order of percentage will highest for

industrial sector which is followed by drinking water, the irrigation sector will have 105.68 percent water. Livestock will require 115.38 percent as compared 2011.

In 2050 the total water will be require 2349 million cubic meter for district as a whole in comparison to 2011. It will increase by 125.74 percent in 2050. The highest utilization of water will be in domestic sector. Which is followed by industrial sector. The livestock sector will require 134.61 percent water in 2050. The irrigation sector will be of the order of 109.77 percent in 2050. It may be concluded that there will be consistent increase of water, particularly in domestic sector which is followed by industrial sector. Livestock and irrigation sector will be of not very importance sector as the irrigation land is fixed and will not enhance in future.

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